

***Tipula* Linnaeus, 1758 (Diptera: Tipulidae) species new to Poland
with notes on the distribution of a further four species**

**Gatunki *Tipula* Linnaeus, 1758 (Diptera: Tipulidae) nowe dla Polski
oraz uwagi o występowaniu czterech innych gatunków z rodzaju**

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ABSTRACT. *Tipula* (*Lunatipula*) *alpina* Loew, 1873, *Tipula* (*Lunatipula*) *helvola* Loew, 1873 and *Tipula* (*Savtshenkia*) *benesignata* Mannheims, 1954 are reported from Poland for the first time in print. New locations for *Tipula* (*Lunatipula*) *livida livida* van der Wulp, 1859, *Tipula* (*Lunatipula*) *pelio stigma* Schummel, 1833, *Tipula* (*Pterelachisus*) *winthemi* Lackschewitz, 1932 and *Tipula* (*Yamatotipula*) *lateralis* Meigen, 1804 – which are species omitted from, or listed as doubtful in the most recent checklist of Polish Tipulidae – are provided confirming the presence of these species in Poland. The distribution, biology and ecology of each species are briefly summarised.

KEY WORDS: Diptera, Tipulidae, craneflies, first records, faunistics, Poland

INTRODUCTION

Tipulidae is a species-rich family of Tipulomorpha with around 4300 described extant species worldwide, of which nearly 630 can be found in the Western Palearctic (Oosterbroek 2022). With the exception of Ctenophorinae, on which several papers have been published in the last 20 years (e.g. Bąkowski et al. 2011, Żurawlew et al. 2016), the tipulid fauna of Poland is greatly under-researched. Data on the occurrence of Polish Tipulinae during this time period is scarce and often in the form of short mentions in larger studies (e.g. Chaniecka et Wiedeńska 2006, Kehlmaier et Floren 2009, Oosterbroek 2009, Kowalczyk et Senn 2017, Heiß 2019). The only paper devoted to the subfamily since the year 2000 is that of Chaniecka (2001) on the occurrence of *Tipula* (*Savtshenkia*) *simulans* Savchenko, 1966 in the Gorce mountains, whilst the last studies of which a significant part concerns Tipulidae are those of Sakwa (1962) and Szadziewski (1983). Another issue is that the number of Tipulidae species recorded in Poland differs depending on the source used. This is in part caused by some species being overlooked in the first checklist of the Tipulidae of present-day Poland

(Krzemiński 1991). Furthermore, in the second, newest checklist (Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007), which provides an update to the former, several of the previously absent species were added, although with the reservation that their occurrence in the country is doubtful and needs to be confirmed. The list of Polish Tipulidae in the Catalogue of the Craneflies of the World, the CCW (Oosterbroek 2022), despite being the most complete and up-to-date source also lacks certain species. As such, I am currently gathering and revising the Polish literature (Syratt *in prep.*), on the basis of which I can state that at least 100 species from the family have been recorded up to date within the current boundaries of Poland compared to the 93 species listed on the CCW. Considering there is a need for confirming the occurrence of several species in Poland, as well as the fact that the revised number of Tipulidae species recorded from the country so far is lower than that of most neighbouring countries (Oosterbroek 2022), I have started studies on the family of which the preliminary results are presented in this paper.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study is based on material collected during several day trips to various localities in Poland (deposited in the author's collection), as well as on preliminary results of an ongoing revision of the Tipulomorpha specimens deposited in the Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals, Polish Academy of Sciences in Kraków (ISEA PAS). The specimens are kept in 70% ethanol or pinned with the cleared terminalia stored in microvials filled with glycerine. Photographs were taken using a Nikon SMZ25 stereomicroscope equipped with a Nikon DS-Ri2 digital camera or with a Nikon COOLPIX P900 camera equipped with a Raynox DCR-250 macro lens in the case of *Tipula (Lunatipula) livida livida* van der Wulp, 1859. Nomenclature, distribution and flight periods are in accordance to Oosterbroek (2022), unless otherwise stated. Physico-geographical mesoregions are as understood in Solon et al. (2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tipula (Lunatipula) alpina Loew, 1873

MATERIAL EXAMINED (1 ♂). **Olkusz Upland (Wyżyna Olkuska)**. Ojców National Park buffer zone: Biały Kościół – Kresy, forest-meadow ecotone, UTM DA16, 27 VI 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt.

FIG. 1. *Tipula (Lunatipula) alpina* male: hypopygium (a – caudal, b – lateral)

Found throughout Europe from Great Britain and France to Belarus, Romania, and southern Scandinavia. **First record for Poland.**

Dufour (1986) lists *T. (L.) alpina* as a thermophilic species favouring deciduous forests, and contrary to its name, not associated with alpine habitats. In Great Britain the species is considered a limestone woodland specialist (Stubbs 2018). Limestone streams (Dufour 2003), gardens (Tillier et Dehalleux 2019), and meadows bordering beech forests (Heiß 2017) are among other habitats where adults have been observed, with the last of these examples being comparable to the site near Ojców National Park. Larvae have been found to live in moist woodland soil, under bark, and in decaying fallen trees and tree stumps such as *Fagus* (Chiswell 1956, Gibbs 2008). Flight period is from April to August.

Tipula (Lunatipula) helvola Loew, 1873

MATERIAL EXAMINED (6 ♂♂, 14 ♀♀). **Poznań Lakeland (Pojezierze Poznańskie)**. Poznań, Cytadela Park, gully, UTM XU30, 12 VII 2021, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt. **Siewierz Basin (Kotlina Siewierza)**. Eagle's Nests Landscape Park (Park Krajobrazowy Orlich Gniazd): Chechło, Centuria river, UTM CA97, 6 VII 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt. **Olkusz Upland (Wyżyna Olkuska)**. Ojców National Park buffer zone: Biały Kościół – Iwiny, Stodoliska gully, UTM DA15, 27 VI 2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Ojców National Park buffer zone: Biały Kościół – Kresy, forest-meadow ecotone, UTM DA16, 27 VI 2021, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Ojców National Park buffer zone: Prądnik Korzkiewski, Prądnik river, UTM DA15, 27 VI 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt; Ojców National Park buffer zone: Smardzowice – Peperówka, forest-meadow ecotone, UTM DA16, 26 VI 2021, 3 ♀♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Ojców National Park buffer zone: Pod Świerki gully, UTM DA15, 27 VI 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt. **Karkonosze Mts.** Karpacz, drainage ditch in pine forest near Władysław Orkan St., 585-600 m a.s.l., UTM WS52, 16 VIII 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt; Karpacz, pine forest near Jan Kasprowicz St., 630 m a.s.l., UTM WS52, 15 VIII 2021, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Karpacz, Skałka stream, pine forest, 620 m a.s.l., UTM WS52, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt. **Beskid Wyspowy Mts.** Szczebel Mt. massif, pine forest, 415 m a.s.l., UTM DA20, 2 VIII 2021, 2 ♀♀, leg. det. M. Syratt. **Beskid Mały Mts.** Mucharz, UTM CA91, 6 VIII 1978, 2 ♀♀, leg. W. Krzemiński, det. J. Martinovský, coll. ISEA PAS.

A widespread West-Palaeartic species, seemingly increasing in abundance and range e.g. in Great Britain, possibly due to climate change (Stubbs 2021).

T. (L.) helvola has been previously reported from Warsaw on the CCW (Stolarczyk *in litt.*, after Oosterbroek 2022). The records presented herein are the first from Poland published in a journal.

Citing various authors, Oosterbroek and de Jong (2001) indicate dry woodland as the preferred habitat, noting that adults usually occur in the damper areas of such environments. This is reflected in the types of habitats where the examined material was collected from; most specimens were found in the immediate vicinity of rivers or humid gullies, and in the instances where “pine forest” is indicated as the habitat in the Karkonosze and Beskid Wyspowy mountains, a stream was always present nearby. Flight period in Europe is from May to September.

Tipula (Lunatipula) livida livida van der Wulp, 1859

MATERIAL EXAMINED (3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀). **Belchatów Upland (Wysoczyzna Belchatowska)**. Tuszyn, UTM CC91/DC01, 19-21 VI 1980, 1 ♀; 26 VI 1980, 1 ♂; 3 VIII 1980, 1 ♂, leg. B. Soszyński, det. J. Martinovský, coll. ISEA PAS. **Częstochowa Upland (Wyżyna Częstochowska)**. Klucze-Osada, Biała Przemsza river, UTM CA97, 5 VII 2021, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Klucze-Osada, pine forest, UTM CA97, 6 VII 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt. **Olkusz Upland (Wyżyna Olkuska)**. Ojców National Park (photo observation – Fig. 2): Prądnik river near Młyny, under bridge, UTM DA16, 23 VI 2021, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Ojców National Park buffer zone: Pod Świerki gully, UTM DA15, 27 VI 2021, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt.

FIG. 2. *Tipula (Lunatipula) livida livida* female observed in Ojców National Park near Młyny: a – habitus, b – ovipositor (lateral), c – ovipositor (dorsal)

Widespread throughout the Western Palearctic, it has also recently been found in East Kazakhstan, though it was noted that the specimen had some differences compared to European males, perhaps being a new subspecies (Devyatkov 2021).

Mannheims (1968) mentions collecting specimens of the species from Poland yet gives no further details on the exact location. *T. (L.) livida* is absent from both Polish checklists of Tipulidae (Krzemiński 1991, Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007). Additionally, photos of the subspecies from Warsaw can be found on the CCW website (Oosterbroek 2022).

T. (L.) livida is a species favouring heaths and woodlands of various types, from thermophilous broad-leaved forests to more humid pine forests and alder groves (Oosterbroek et de Jong 2001, citing various authors). Adults have also been found in steppic meadows (Ujvárosi 2002), and grasslands (Oosterbroek 2002). Larvae live under moss, in leaf litter, dead wood, detritus and damp sandy soils (Podėnienė 2000, Oosterbroek et de Jong 2001, citing various authors). Flight period is mostly May to August.

Tipula (Lunatipula) peliostigma Schummel, 1833

MATERIAL EXAMINED (4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀). **Kraków Bridge (Pomost Krakowski)**. Kraków – Bronowice Małe, UTM DA14, reared from wet leaf litter in gutter (mainly *Fraxinus excelsior* L. and *Corylus avellana* L. leaves), 4th instar larvae collected 9 V 2020, adult emergence 2-14 VI 2020, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 4th instar larva collected 18 IV 2021, adult emergence 28 V 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt; Kraków – Bronowice Małe, Struga Bronowicka stream, UTM DA14, reared from under bark of fallen *Fraxinus excelsior*, 4th instar larva collected 28 IV 2021, adult emergence 10 VI 2021, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt.

Found throughout the Western Palearctic, as well as East Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan.

Described from Wrocław (Schummel 1833), Mannheims (1965) later confirmed the presence of the species at the *locus typicus*. In addition, a figure in Theowald's (1957) work is of an outer gonostylus of a specimen from Wrocław. The species has also been recorded from Kraków (Nowicki 1870) and Puławy in the Masovian Lowland (Savchenko 1964). The CCW (Oosterbroek 2022) lists *T. (L.) peliostigma* from Poland and contains photos of adults from Warsaw. The species was not, however, included in Krzemiński's (1991) checklist and its occurrence in the country is noted as doubtful and needing confirmation in the newer checklist (Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007).

A thermophilic species of dry woodland and grassland, and hedgerows, with the latter being a much preferred habitat in the UK (Dufour 1986, Heiss 2017, Stubbs 2021). Larvae can be found in leaf litter, under moss in broad-leaved forests, and in dead wood (Oosterbroek et de Jong 2001, citing various authors). Interestingly, in Great Britain it seems to be an old bird nest specialist; the species has been reared from robin, blackbird and song thrush nests (Stubbs 2021, citing various authors).

The Polish specimens reared from wet leaf litter were found together with *Tipula (Lunatipula) selene* Meigen, 1830. Flight period is from April to August.

Tipula (Pterelachisus) winthemi Lackschewitz, 1932

Syn.: *Tipula hortensis* Meigen *sensu* Schummel, 1833; Theowald 1980

MATERIAL EXAMINED (1 ♀). **Olkusz Upland (Wyżyna Olkuska)**. Kraków Valleys Landscape Park (Park Krajobrazowy Dolinki Krakowskie): Będkowska Valley, UTM DA15, 15 V 1983, 1 ♀, leg. W. Krzemiński, det. C. Dufour, coll. ISEA PAS.

FIG. 3. *Tipula (Pterelachisus) winthemi* female: a – ovipositor (lateral), b – right wing

Distributed throughout the Palearctic from Northern Spain to Kamchatka, seemingly becoming rare in most of its range during the last century (Theowald 1980).

The species has been previously reported from Poland, with one female recorded from Puławy (Savchenko 1964). Furthermore, Theowald (1980) notes that based on the description, Schummel's (1833) records of *Tipula hortensis* Meigen from the vicinity of Wrocław are probably in fact *Tipula (Pterelachisus) winthemi*. Similarly, a male in the Schummel collection in the Natural History Museum Vienna originally identified as *T. hortensis* was found to be *T. (P.) winthemi* (Theowald 1980). Despite this, *T. (P.) winthemi* is absent both from the Polish Tipulidae checklists (Krzemiński 1991, Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007) and the CCW (Oosterbroek 2022).

A largely lotic species, found near streams and headwater brooks, as well as moist heath forests and spruce mires, beech and mixed forests (Gelhaus et Podenas 2006, Salmela 2009, Carles-Tolrá 2019). The specimen from the Kraków Valleys Landscape Park was collected near a stream in a karst valley. Larvae have been mentioned from stones under moss, in the accumulated soil (Yadamsuren et al. 2015). Flight period is from April to July (Oosterbroek 2022).

Tipula (Savtshenka) benesignata Mannheims, 1954

MATERIAL EXAMINED (1 ♂). **Kraków Bridge (Pomost Krakowski)**. Kraków – Bronowice Male, Struga Bronowicka stream, UTM DA14, 25 IX 2020, 1 ♂, leg. det. M. Syratt.

Widespread in Europe, recorded from Greece to Scandinavia and France, as well as Russia (Kareliya, Leningradskaya oblast, Moskovskaya oblast, North Caucasus), Turkey (Bursa, Canakkale) and Kyrgyzstan (Tien Mountains). **First record for Poland.**

FIG. 4. Habitat of *Tipula (Savtshenka) benesignata* in Kraków

The habitat and further biology have been relatively well studied by Przhiboro (2003, 2009); larvae are known to be abundant in tufts of wet moss in the water margin zones of lakes, limnocrone springs and streams. The species has been characterised as a possible polysaprophage with elements of bryophagy and facultative predation – an examination of larval gut contents identified the three main components to be fragments of mosses, remains of ceratopogonid pupae (in some cases along with appendages of pharate adults), and conifer pollen grains. Other habitats from which the species has been reported are suburban gardens (Hofsvang 1987) and mountainous coniferous forests including mossy fir forests and larch forests (Ujvárosi 2002, Dufour 2003, Tillier et Oosterbroek 2019). The site in Kraków (Fig. 4) is a shallow stream in a human-modified fragment of alder riparian forest (Dubiel 2001). Tufts of wet moss on rocks and logs are present but overall scarce. Flight period is from August to October.

Tipula (Yamatotipula) lateralis Meigen, 1804

MATERIAL EXAMINED (4 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀). **Drwęca Valley (Dolina Drwęcy)**. Bratian, UTM DE02, 26 VII 1980, 1 ♂, leg. N. Nadachowski, det. J. Martinovský, coll. ISEA PAS. **Kraków Bridge (Pomost Krakowski)**. Kraków – Bronowice Małe, Rudawa river, UTM DA14, 29 IX 2020, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Kraków – Mydlniki, Wapiennik, drainage ditch, UTM DA14, 3 IX 2020, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. det. M. Syratt; Kraków – Wola Justowska, *ad lucem*, UTM DA14, 6 VIII 1985, 1 ♀; 9 VIII 1985, 1 ♀, leg. J. Kozielec, det. M. Syratt, coll. ISEA PAS. **Bochnia Foothills (Podgórze Bocheńskie)**. Niepołomice Forest near Szarów, UTM DA43, 21 V 1978, 1 ♂, leg. W. Krzemiński, det. J. Martinovský, coll. ISEA PAS.

Widespread and common in the Western Palearctic, as well as being reported from East Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan.

T. (Y.) lateralis has been recorded from numerous sites in Poland (Schummel 1833, Nowicki 1864, Grzegorzek 1873, Czwalina 1893, Riedel 1919, Demel 1922, Savchenko 1961, Sakwa 1962, Szczesny 1974). Listed from Poland in the CCW (Oosterbroek 2022), the species is absent from Krzemiński's checklist (1991) and listed as doubtful and requiring confirmation in the latest checklist (Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007).

An ecologically flexible species, being ubiquitous provided there is a lack of shade and a presence of wet sediment needed for the larvae. Margins of rivers, streams, ponds and lakes, as well as gravel pits, ditches, marshes, coastal landslips, rich fens, seepages in meadows, moors and limestone screes are all suitable habitats (Dufour 1986, 2003, Autio et Salmela 2010, Stubbs 2021). Larva have been found at the bottom of small rivers, hygropetrica, sand and silt in the riparian zone of small rivulets and large rivers and in the littoral zone of lakes, mud on the slopes of lakes and rivers and in bogs, clay, and mosses on the banks of rivulets and land-improvement channels (Podènienè 2003). Under laboratory conditions *T. (Y.) lateralis* larvae preferred to feed on *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. leaves over *Quercus faginea* Lam. and *Eucalyptus globulus* Labill. leaves (Graça 2001, citing Canhoto et Graça 1992, 1995). Lekking behaviour has been observed in adult males (Smith 2018). Flight period is from March to September.

SUMMARY

Three species are recorded as new to Poland for the first time in print: *Tipula (Lunatipula) alpina* Loew, 1873, *Tipula (Lunatipula) helvola* Loew, 1873 and *Tipula (Savtshenkia) benesignata* Mannheims, 1954.

Four species omitted from, or listed as doubtful in the latest checklist of Polish Tipulidae (Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007): *Tipula (Lunatipula) livida livida* van der Wulp, 1859, *Tipula (Lunatipula) peliostigma* Schummel, 1833, *Tipula (Pterelachisus) winthemi* Lackschewitz, 1932, and *Tipula (Yamatotipula) lateralis*, are confirmed to occur in the country.

Comparing the preliminary number of Tipulidae species recorded from Poland with that of neighbouring countries it is highly probable, that there are many more species still to be found from the territory of Poland.

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PODSUMOWANIE

Tipulidae to liczna w gatunki rodzina muchówek, która jednak nie jest w Polsce dostatecznie zbadana. Ponadto, z powodu sprzeczności w literaturze (w tym w spisach gatunków występujących w faunie Polski), ustalenie dokładnej liczby gatunków wykazanych dotychczas z terenu kraju w obecnych jego granicach jest utrudnione. W najnowszej checkliście (Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007) występowanie niektórych gatunków na terenie Polski zostało uznane za wątpliwe i wymagające potwierdzenia.

W niniejszej pracy ukazują się po raz pierwszy w druku rekordy trzech gatunków nowych dla Polski: *Tipula (Lunatipula) alpina* Loew, 1873, *Tipula (Lunatipula) helvola* Loew, 1873 oraz *Tipula (Savtshenkia) benesignata* Mannheims, 1954.

Dla kolejnych czterech gatunków pominiętych, lub których występowanie w Polsce uznano za wątpliwe w ostatnim wykazie Tipulidae (Skibińska et Chudzicka 2007): *Tipula (Lunatipula) livida livida* van der Wulp, 1859, *Tipula (Lunatipula) peliostigma* Schummel, 1833, *Tipula (Pterelachisus) winthemi* Lackschewitz, 1932 oraz *Tipula (Yamatotipula) lateralis* Meigen, 1804, przedstawiono nowe stanowiska, tym samym potwierdzając ich występowanie na terenie kraju.

Biorąc pod uwagę fakt, że wstępna liczba gatunków z rodziny dotychczas wykazanych z Polski jest niższa od liczby podawanej w większości państw ościennych, należy się spodziewać odnalezienia wielu kolejnych gatunków w przyszłości.

<http://pte.au.poznan.pl/dipteron/redakcja.htm>

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